

D7.5

Communication strategy and plan – Version II

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547
Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP7 – Dissemination, exploitation and international cooperation
Deliverable number	D7.6 Communication tools - Version II
Status - version, date	V1.0, 31/03/2024
Deliverable leader	ERTICO – ITS Europe
Contractual date of delivery	31/03/2024
Keywords	PoDIUM, Communication, strategy, plan, target audience, key message

Contributors

Name	Organisation
Sevi Christoforou	ICCS
Martin Dirnwöber	ATE
Nikoletta Karitsioti	ICCS
Emily Stevens	ATE

Quality Control

	Name	Organisation	Date
Peer review 1	Ioannis Neokosmidis	INC	06/03/2024
Peer review 2	Fabrizio Gatti, Ezio Chiocchetti	TIM	13/03/2024

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
01	16/02/2024	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	First draft of document
02	26/02/2024	Sevi Christoforou - ICCS	Suggestions for improvement and additions to Chapter 3
03	01/03/2024	Céline Lefort- ERTICO	Clean version with suggestions incorporated

04	14/03/2024	Céline Lefort – ERTICO	Improvements after internal review
1.0	21/03/2024	Céline Lefort – ERTICO	Finalisation of the document

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Table of contents

Contributors.....	2
Quality Control.....	2
Version History	2
Legal Disclaimer	3
List of figures.....	5
List of tables.....	5
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	6
Executive Summary.....	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1. Project introduction	8
1.2. Purpose of the deliverable	8
1.3. Intended audience.....	9
2. PoDIUM communication strategy.....	10
2.1. Statement of Purpose.....	10
2.2. Communication goals and objectives.....	10
2.3. SWOT analysis	12
3. PoDIUM communication plan	14
3.1. Target audience and key messages.....	14
3.2. Visual identity.....	16
3.3. Communication tools and channels	16
3.4. Communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).....	17
3.5. Risk management	18
4. Roles and responsibilities.....	20
5. Conclusion.....	21
References	22

List of figures

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis for PoDIUM’s communication strategy	13
Figure 2: PoDIUM logo and colours.....	16

List of tables

Table 1: PoDIUM’s communication goals and objectives	11
Table 2: PoDIUM target groups and key messages.....	14
Table 3: List of communication KPIs.....	17
Table 4: PoDIUM’s communication plan risk management.....	18

No table of figures entries found.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the second version of the communication strategy and plan of the PoDIUM project. It provides an update of the strategy that is followed and of the communication goals and objectives of the project to maximise the impact of the project's communication. The review of the communication plan includes a revision of the audiences that are targeted by the communication efforts, as well as of the key messages. This document also provides an overview of the communication tools, channels, and activities that have been deployed by the project up to M18 and updates when applicable and necessary. The roles and responsibilities of the PoDIUM partners regarding the communication efforts are also outlined in this document.

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 (Introduction) contains a brief description of PoDIUM, describes the purpose of this deliverable and provides information on the target audience of the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 (PoDIUM communication strategy) explains the purpose behind the communication strategy and how it works with the dissemination strategy, provides an update of the communication goals and objectives of PoDIUM, and proposes a SWOT analysis.
- Chapter 3 (PoDIUM communication plan) presents the revised communication plan of PoDIUM, which includes the project's, target audience and key messages, visual identity, and various communication tools and channels. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and a plan for risk management are also proposed.
- Chapter 4 (Roles and responsibilities) outlines the roles and responsibilities of the consortium members within Work Package (WP) 7, as well the involvement of the whole consortium in the communication and dissemination efforts.
- Chapter 5 (Conclusion) consists of concluding remarks.

This deliverable is the updated version of D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan*. It introduces some changes to the first version of the communication strategy and plan to ensure its success and impact.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable D7.5 *Communication strategy and plan – Version II* is to update the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan to maximise the impact and outreach of the project, describing in detail the reviewed strategy and plan to be followed by the consortium of PoDIUM. It provides information on the key messages and target audience, as well as the communication channels and instruments to advance the strategic objectives of PoDIUM.

This document is complementary to Deliverables D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines*, D7.6 *Communication tools – Version II*, D7.4 *Dissemination plan*, and D7.8 *Exploitation plan – Version II*. Deliverable D7.1 explains the brand identity and guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand, including the project's logo, typography, and various visual elements to be used in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project by the partners. Deliverable D7.6 presents an update of the different communication tools developed as part of the project to support its communication strategy. Deliverable D7.4 defines the PoDIUM dissemination objectives and plan, as well as dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and all dissemination activities of the project, including events, journals, etc. The communication strategy and plan, and the dissemination strategy and plan therefore work together to achieve the success of PoDIUM's communication and dissemination efforts. Deliverable D7.8 focuses on the update of exploitation plan for PoDIUM. It also defines business metrics, legal rights, obligations, and procedures on intellectual property rights.

1.3. Intended audience

This is a public document. For the consortium of PoDIUM, this document serves as a reference on the key messages, channels and target groups to support the communication around the project. For external stakeholders and the broader public, this deliverable provides information on the communication objectives of PoDIUM, as well as key aspects of its communication plan.

2. PoDIUM communication strategy

2.1. Statement of Purpose

The PoDIUM communication strategy establishes a framework that allows PoDIUM to raise awareness and create understanding and high visibility of the project's activities and outcomes to the stakeholders targeted. The communication activities of the project aim to foster stakeholder engagement and involvement in the project's progress and results. To ensure the long-lasting impact of the project's results, an integrated and common plan has therefore been devised for the whole consortium. As the project reached the midpoint of its journey, the communication strategy has been revised to guarantee that it is still relevant and adapted to the project's strategic objectives, by ensuring the maximum impact of communication efforts.

The strategy and plan set out in this deliverable focus mainly on the communication activities of PoDIUM. While communication and dissemination (as well as exploitation) activities are often carried out together, they fulfil different functions. Communication activities revolve around the promotion of the project's actions and results, while dissemination concerns making the project's results public through publications in scientific magazines and participation in events, among other activities. All dissemination activities that will be carried out in the project need to be promoted and communicated to the right stakeholders using the right communication channels, following a clear and well-designed strategy, which is set out in the following section.

2.2. Communication goals and objectives

To amplify the strategic objectives of the project, the PoDIUM communication strategy has set several goals and objectives, which are presented in Table 1. The goals represent an achievable outcome on the longer term, while the objectives define specific and measurable actions on the shorter term to achieve the goals. To guide the communication efforts of the project, SMART objectives (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, and Time-bound) have been outlined.

The communication strategy of PoDIUM is tailored to the different phases of the project's lifespan, which entail different communication activities. During the initial phase, the project successfully built a solid and recognisable brand identity, including guidelines for its correct use for the consortium. The main focus was on raising awareness of PoDIUM and its objectives. Communication channels were set up and promotional materials were created to facilitate that goal. As the project is now in its second phase, communication activities concentrate on engaging stakeholders and creating visibility of the project's developments and progress. Communication efforts focus on promoting all dissemination activities of the project and on the progress and latest developments of the project, including through local media. In the last stage of the project, widely communicating and promoting PoDIUM's results and final event will be the central aspects, mainly through website and social media posting, and at least one press release at the beginning of the project and for the final event, and at least one joint press release about the demonstrations in the Living Labs.

The communication goals and objectives of PoDIUM support the dissemination activities of the project by helping to promote and communicate the project's publications, participation in conferences, trade

shows or any other event, workshops and webinars, and the demonstrations in the three PoDIUM Living Labs.

Table 1: PoDIUM’s communication goals and objectives

Goal	Communication objectives	Communication means	Timeline
<p>Raise awareness and understanding of the project and its objectives among stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a strong and identifiable brand identity and develop cohesive communication materials based on it, to ensure the impactful representation of PoDIUM. • Provide clear guidelines on the use of the PoDIUM brand identity for the consortium. • Create the project’s communication channels (including the website and social media channels) and materials (including a roll-up banner, flyer, and poster). • Press release, articles and posts on social media to introduce PoDIUM and its objectives. • Identify the target audience and determine key messages. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand identity document • Word and PowerPoint templates • Internal dissemination and communication procedure tools and documents • Press release • Social media posts about PoDIUM • PoDIUM communication strategy and plan • Website set up and launch • Promotion of the flyer and poster through online channels 	<p>M1-M09</p>
<p>Communicate the project’s activities and progress to the right target audience through the right channels</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make use of the project’s communication materials, tools, and channels to promote the progress of PoDIUM (website updates with publications, deliverables, presentations, etc., and promotion of these updates on social media). • Identify and engage with the media, including local media. • Ensure a strong online presence through the project’s website and social media channels, with regular articles and posts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly articles on the PoDIUM website and posts on PoDIUM’s X/Twitter and LinkedIn channels • At least 1 article on each Living Lab in local media 	<p>M10-M24</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote all dissemination events and activities using the right communication tools and channels. • Create promotional material for webinars, exhibitions, trials etc. such as digital banners, registration pages, stickers, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of the project’s videos • Two newsletters per year • Events section of the website is kept up-to-date and events are promoted on social media 	
<p>Communicate the project’s final results</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate the project’s final results through website updates and promote these updates on social media. • Final press release about the project’s final event. • Promote the final event of the project through articles on the PoDIUM website and social media posts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 2 articles on the project’s website about the final results of the project • Continue promoting the project videos. • Final event has been promoted on social media, and at least 2 articles about it on the PoDIUM website. • 1 final press release 	<p>M25-M36</p>

2.3. SWOT analysis

A SWOT analysis (Figure 1) has been carried out to provide an overview of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats regarding the achievement of the PoDIUM communication objectives. This analysis helped to identify points where more efforts and solutions might be needed, based on short and medium-term predictions. By building on the project’s strengths and by taking into account potential weaker aspects, the SWOT analysis helps create a strong and successful communication strategy for PoDIUM. The SWOT analysis has been reviewed in this document to ensure the communication efforts are as successful as possible.

The strengths identified remain relevant. The partners’ own channels have been leveraged as much as possible, especially the ERTICO channels, which have a wide outreach. The partners are regularly reminded to engage with PoDIUM’s posts on social media and share news items to their own networks.

The project partners have already contributed to several news items published on the PoDIUM website, providing opportunities to delve deeper into specific aspects of the project. Three articles presenting the Living Labs have also been published, providing more details on the use cases they will demonstrate. The initial liaison activities carried out have also resulted in interesting communication opportunities. Local media will be leveraged more in the coming months as the activities in the Living Labs ramp up. The uncertainty around the X/Twitter platform has not led so far to a switch to another platform, as engagement on that platform has been in line with the KPIs set in this deliverable. Similarly, the technical aspects of the project have not made public outreach too difficult for the moment, thanks to a focus on making this kind of information easy to understand for the general public on the project website.

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis for PoDIUM's communication strategy

3. PoDIUM communication plan

To achieve the objectives and goals of the PoDIUM communication and dissemination strategy, a communication plan has been created at M06 and revised at M18, to ensure that the communication efforts are on the right track and aligned with the strategy described in this document. The communication plan sets out the updated key messages and target audience of the project. It also provides a brief overview of the communication tools, channels and activities that will be used to reach the communication objectives of PoDIUM. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is also proposed to monitor and report the impact of the communication plan, as well as a plan for risk management. The plan also includes an overview of the roles and responsibilities of the consortium partners.

3.1. Target audience and key messages

PoDIUM’s communication activities target specific stakeholder categories through specific communication methods. The target audience are groups for whom the project results have potential implications and benefits at the policy, economic, technological, and societal levels. The different groups have been identified and agreed on by the consortium partners in the Grant Agreement. The PoDIUM consortium will engage with the identified stakeholders through different channels. Although the list has been revised in this second version of the communication plan, it remains non-exhaustive and will be continuously reviewed in order to ensure that the right audience is targeted.

To guarantee the effective and impactful promotion of PoDIUM, a set of key messages has been defined and tailored to each target audience. This will ensure the maximum impact of the communication and dissemination efforts. Both the target audiences and key messages are detailed in Table 2.

In addition to the specific messages for the different target groups, different key elements about the project are continuously conveyed across the project’s channels to reinforce PoDIUM’s key messages. The following messages are therefore central to the communication around the project:

- PoDIUM aims to reach higher levels of vehicle automation and foster the development of advanced CCAM solutions;
- PoDIUM builds trust and sustainability for CCAM;
- PoDIUM advances key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure;
- PoDIUM works towards software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data;
- PoDIUM demonstrates advanced CCAM use cases in real traffic conditions.

Table 2: PoDIUM target groups and key messages

Target group	Key message	Communication methods
Industries Including sectors involved in the project: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) & software suppliers,	PoDIUM will demonstrate demanding CCAM UCs to advance a set of key PDI technologies to reach higher levels of automation. The project will open up new business opportunities that will	Project website, social media, non-scientific articles, scientific articles, newsletters, project

<p>infrastructure suppliers, telecommunication operators, information providers, Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), road operators, Traffic Management Centre (TMC) operators, etc.</p>	<p>benefit from the PoDIUM’s multi-connectivity and interoperability approach which enables the development of new traffic management processes.</p>	<p>brochure, project video.</p>
<p>Institutions Including but not limited to: policy and decision makers at European and national level, standardisation bodies, national or regional funding bodies, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM focuses on the interoperability, reliability, redundancy, and multi-connectivity aspects of the technologies tested to promote exchange and joint learning between stakeholders involved at national and international levels. PoDIUM will contribute to the acceleration of the deployment of advanced CCAM services in Europe, helping maintain the EU leadership in innovation related to CCAM services.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, non-scientific articles, scientific articles, project brochure, project video.</p>
<p>Scientific and research community Including but not limited to: academic and research centres, operators of test sites to integrate piloted technologies for future applications, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM aims to advance key PDI technologies, including data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment, environment perception modals, digital twins, and new C-ITS messages. PoDIUM will promote scientific excellence and foster open science principles through high-quality scientific publications.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, scientific articles, newsletters, project brochure, project video.</p>
<p>Users Including but not limited to: sector organisations representing industry end users, user groups impacted by developed technologies, end-user associations, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM will contribute to building trust and sustainability for CCAM services, improve EU road users’ experience and reduce general traffic travel time. By providing real time notifications about emergency cases, PoDIUM will assist towards increased safety and increased effectiveness of emergency services and protection of VRUs.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, articles in magazines, newsletters, project video.</p>
<p>General public Including but not limited to: anyone interested in innovation, transport, mobility, CCAM, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM will advance technologies to bolster the deployment of automated vehicles. The project will help contribute to improving road safety, the effectiveness of emergency services, and traffic flow, and help reduce emissions.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, newsletters, project brochure.</p>

3.2. Visual identity

To ensure a strong visual identity and maximum visibility of PoDIUM, as well as the consistent and coherent use and representation of the PoDIUM brand by the consortium, the brand identity and guidelines of the project have been developed at M03. The brand identity and guidelines include the logo, typography, colours and visual elements to be used in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project.

The correct guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand are provided in Deliverable D7.1 *Brand Identity and guidelines*.

Figure 2: PoDIUM logo and colours

3.3. Communication tools and channels

A wide range of communication tools, materials, and channels have been developed as part of the PoDIUM project to ensure a constant flow of information, raise awareness of the project, and reach out the target audience. The tools and channels include:

- **PoDIUM website** (www.podium-project.eu) contains the main information about the project, presented in a clear and concise way. It represents the primary access point and knowledge base of the project. The website is updated regularly with information on participation in events and other activities and at least 10 **news articles** per year. This ensures that the content of the website remains interesting for both new and returning visitors, and that the project’s activities and results are promoted in an engaging way. News articles cover various topics such as presentations of the PoDIUM Living Labs and of the consortium members, and any other project developments.
- **Social media** (X/Twitter: [@PoDIUM_EU](https://twitter.com/PoDIUM_EU) and LinkedIn: [PoDIUM Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/podium-project)) are used to share regular news and updates about the project and engage with a wider audience. Regular posts on social media channels allow for more interaction with relevant stakeholders. The PoDIUM consortium is expected to actively contribute to the project’s social media activities.

- A **newsletter** is sent twice a year and circulated through the project’s website and social media channels. It provides the latest project news, upcoming events, progress and achievements, which aim to appeal to the different stakeholders and help increase the awareness about PoDIUM and its results.
- **Videos** will be created from the beginning of the second year of the project to promote PoDIUM’s work and raise awareness of its activities. The first video will be an introductory animated video, presenting PoDIUM’s main information. The other videos will focus on the project’s progress and results.
- **Webinars** will be organised by the consortium to present important project milestones and to raise awareness about the objectives and activities in the different Living Labs. The consortium will also seek opportunities to organise or participate in webinars with C-Roads and other EU-funded projects.
- A **roll-up banner** has been developed to bring high visibility to PoDIUM to the wider audience at various events and exhibitions.
- A **leaflet and a poster** have been produced to provide more information on PoDIUM and its objectives. They are available online on the project’s website and are distributed at various external events.
- **Digital communication material** was designed, such as digital banners, infographics, etc. to showcase project activities and results.
- **Ad hoc promotional material** such as stickers, flags, etc. will be produced to increase the project’s visibility during trials and demonstrations.
- **Press releases** will be prepared and published by the consortium at key moments of the project to communicate important information and promote major events and milestones, such as the project demonstrations and the PoDIUM final event. Partners will be responsible for the translation of the press release in their language and its distribution to local media.

All communication tools developed as part of the project are described in more detail in Deliverable D7.6 *Communication tools*. Their current status and achievements are also provided in D7.6, as well as their performance regarding the KPIs.

3.4. Communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

All communication activities must have the expected impact on the target audience and help advance the project’s goals. PoDIUM has defined a set of quantitative indicators to monitor and evaluate the impact and targets of the communication plan and ensure its success. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of PoDIUM’s communication activities are presented in Table 3. KPIs related to dissemination activities are thoroughly described in D7.4 *Dissemination Plan*.

Table 3: List of communication KPIs

Tools/Channels	Key Performance Indicator	Target value		
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Communication tools	Website: Total visits per month	>50	>100	>150
	X/Twitter: PoDIUM hashtags	60	100	140

LinkedIn: Number of followers of PoDIUM page	75	100	150
Video: Number produced	>1	>2	>2
Project brochure: Number produced	1	Update	Update
Technical leaflets: Published and distributed	>100	>100	>100
Webinars: Number organised/participants	1/50	2/50	2/50

All PoDIUM communication activities are duly collected and monitored by ERTICO as WP7 leader. Monthly WP7 calls and regular meetings with the consortium are used to report and assess the communication efforts. Periodic reports and D7.6 *Communication tools* are the main documents used to report the progress of the communication activities of the project.

3.5. Risk management

To anticipate potential risks to the success of the communication plan, Table 4 lists potential risks and their likelihood, and suggests mitigation measures to minimise associated impact. This list has been reviewed and updated in the second version of this deliverable, ensuring it remains current and relevant.

Table 4: PoDIUM’s communication plan risk management

Risk	Likelihood (low, medium, high)	Mitigation
Lack of contribution from the partners to the communication and dissemination efforts	Low	Regular meetings with consortium/follow up emails, reminding to inform about the project’s activities that could be communicated.
Under-reporting of participation at events or partners’ dissemination activities	Medium	Regular reminder at consortium meetings to update the dissemination activities reporting file.
Missed opportunities to participate in events relevant to the project and to promote this on the website/social media	Low	Maintenance of an events calendar, mentioning the deadline to submit sessions, papers, etc.
Not enough posts on social media/posts are not frequent enough	Medium	Remind consortium at meeting to contribute with input for social media posts, leverage the social media channels of the partners to

		create content (reposting/sharing their content).
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4. Roles and responsibilities

All communication and dissemination activities fall under WP7 “Dissemination, exploitation and international cooperation”. ERTICO acts as Work Package leader and leads T7.1 “Communication strategy and tools”. ERTICO therefore coordinates and leads the overall communication activities and is the PoDIUM Communication Manager.

ERTICO will work in close collaboration with ICCS, who leads T7.2 “Dissemination activities and events”. In PoDIUM, ICCS acts as the Dissemination Manager of the project. The other tasks in the Work Package are T7.3 “Liaison activities and international cooperation”, which is led by AustriaTech, and T7.4 “Exploitation strategy and IPR management”, led by ENIDE and Tenalach Consulting.

Almost all consortium members have budget allocated (person-months and other direct costs) in WP7 and are therefore required to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts of PoDIUM. This entails drafting articles for the website, providing useful content for the website and social media, such as infographics, relevant and interesting studies/reports etc., translating content and liaising with local media to disseminate news about the project in their respective countries, monitoring press clippings about the project in local media or published through their own channels, co-organisation of workshops, presentation in conferences and other external events, contact with local media, etc.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the revision of the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan. The strategy outlines the communication goals of the project. The communication plan identifies and describes the target groups for communication and dissemination activities and explains the key messages and channels that are used to reach them. The main communication tools of PoDIUM are briefly listed in this deliverable. They are described in more detail in Deliverable D7.6 *Communication tools*. The plan also provides the KPIs used to monitor the impact of the project's communication plan, as well as how risk management is approached. The roles and responsibilities of the different partners are also addressed.

The detailed dissemination plan and exploitation plan of PoDIUM can be found in Deliverables D7.4 and D7.8 respectively.

References

PoDIUM D7.1 *Brand identity and guidelines* – available [here](#) on the project website.

PoDIUM D7.2 *Communication strategy and plan - Version I* – available [here](#) on the project website.

PoDIUM D7.4 *Dissemination Plan* – available [here](#) on the project website.

PoDIUM D7.6 *Communication tools - Version II*.

PoDIUM D7.8 *Exploitation plan – Version II*.